

Cassava Processing Techniques and the Factors Militating against the Diversification of Cassava Processing: Evidence from Cassava Processors in Imo State

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Abstract: Cassava contributes more to the growth of an economy when processed into diverse forms using modern techniques. A major issue of concern is that the immense potentials in cassava processing have not been achieved in Nigeria and in particular Imo state. This is because cassava processing is still based on traditional techniques and the range of cassava by-products processed is limited. In this study, the nature of cassava processing techniques adopted by cassava processors in Imo State as well as the factors that constrain the diversification of cassava processing into various cassava by-products are examined. The study adopted a multi-stage sampling technique in selecting 216 cassava processors in selected local government areas of the state using structured questionnaires. Descriptive statistics such as percentages, frequency distribution and mean were utilized to analyze the data. The study finds that cassava processing business in the state is dominated by the female sex (70.7%). Also, while secondary school leavers (52.7%) pre-dominate in the processing, majority of them (36.4%) has less than four years of processing experience. Findings also reveal that the processors in the state still process more of the traditional cassava by-products such as fufu (83.2%), garri (94.6%) and tapioca (77.21%). Also, apart from grating in which 84.8% of the processors adopted machine processing technique, manual processing technique pre-dominates. By bringing to focus the dominant cassava by-products processed and the processing techniques adopted by cassava processors in Imo State in addition to the factors that militate against diversifying into the processing of other cassava by-products, this study contributes to the literature. However, the study is limited by the inability to cover the entire state which future studies should aim at so that results can be generalized.

Keywords: *Cassava processing, processing technique, value-addition, cassava by-products, diversification.*

Introduction

In Nigeria, cassava is among the most common and essential staple crops whose production is mainly carried out by smallholder farmers. The attractiveness of cassava as a food crop lies on its unique characteristics. One of the features, according to Ettah and Nweze (2016) is that it is rich in carbohydrates, thus implying that it has numerous end uses. Second, it is available all the year round and this makes it more preferable to other seasonal crops in terms of food security and lastly, it tolerates low soil fertility and it resists drought (Emokaro & Oyoboh, 2016). In Nigeria, Olukunle (2016) observed that cassava tubers are processed into various by-products such as cassava flour, garri, fufu and others. The implication is that in Nigeria, cassava has become regular diets among the household. Cassava has equally been noted to be relevant in boosting a country's income at the international level as demand for cassava derivatives have increased over the last two decades (Miklyae, Jenkins & Shobowale, 2021). According to the information from the federal government of Nigeria reported in the Guardian newspaper of February, 2021, Nigeria is ranked as the highest cassava producer in the world. In support of this, Esiobu, Theresa, Akande,

Udunwa and Emeruwa (2023) observed that presently, Nigeria produces the largest cassava in the world with an annual production capacity of 54 million tons of tuberous roots; being almost 19% of the total world production capacity. Across the states in Nigeria, cassava production is mainly produced in Anambra, Delta, Edo, Benue, Cross River, Kwara, Imo, Oyo, among others. It is against this backdrop that the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA, 2012) contended that the economic livelihood of many Nigerians in the South-east, South-south and Middle-belt revolves around cassava production.

In Imo state, cassava is a key crop that most households produce, thus providing household food security, poverty reduction and sustained means of livelihood (Chidiebere-Mark *et al.*, 2014). The major cassava by-products produced and consumed in the state are *garri*, tapioca and *fufu* (Apeh, *et al.*, 2023). Worthy of note is that these are processed using traditional processing techniques (Igwe, *et al.*, 2025). Despite the fact that the state produces cassava in abundance, the demand for *garri* in particular is very high that supply from other neighboring states such as Etche in Rivers state, Ogoja in Cross Rivers state and

Umunede in Delta state augment domestic supply. It should be stated here that most of the cassava processing in the state is mainly for direct consumption, yet cassava has a lot of derivatives that serve the needs of industries. Among the cassava by-products which are in high demand because of their relevance to the industries are cassava flour, cassava chips and cassava starch. Also, livestock feeds which currently are in high demand both locally and international can be obtained from cassava processing. Cassava processors in Imo state overlook the importance of these by-products which if well harnessed could improve their earning as they could be exported to generate foreign revenue. The traditional technology adopted in cassava processing could be partly blamed for the lack of interest in diversifying into the processing of these cassava by-products. Addressing the constraints to cassava value addition is expected to raise production, increase food availability and enhance income for smallholder farmers. In addition, enlarging cassava derivative products such as chips, cassava flour, starch, etc will provide raw materials for local industries which are necessary in partly replacing their imports and thus reduce the pressure on foreign exchange. The focus of this research is

therefore to examine the nature of cassava processing techniques adopted by cassava processors in Imo state as well as investigate the factors that constrain the diversification into different types of cassava by-products.

Despite the fact that Nigeria currently holds the first position in cassava production in the world, the country's cassava production has not been able to attain its full potential as there is still a supply gap at the global market. The United Nations Industrial Development Organization and Federal Government of Nigeria (UNIDO and FGN, 2016) have noted that in Nigeria, the potential for cassava for industrial utilization has not been adequately realized since over 84 percent of cassava production is consumed as food while only 16 percent is utilized as industrial materials. The relevance of cassava in the quest to achieve food security as well as generate revenue for Nigeria has led to some policies to address the challenges facing cassava production over the years. For instance, there was the Presidential Initiative on Cassava which ran from 2002-2007. Among the objectives of the policy was to encourage the export of processed cassava products (*Okhankhuele et al., 2017*). Also, in order to support cassava processing industry, the federal government

came up with the Cassava Transformation Agenda in 2011 with an objective to increase the demand for cassava flour. However, despite these laudable policies, cassava production and processing is still rudimentary.

In order to address the challenges that constrain the utilization of the full potential in cassava production, there is need to identify the techniques used in cassava production. In Imo state, cassava processing is mainly traditional with low level of value-addition. This situation is also applicable to other cassava producing states in Nigeria as a study in Ogun state by Obayelu, Olaleke, Oke and Oladeji (2018) revealed that traditional method of processing predominates cassava processing in the state. As a result of the adoption of traditional processing technology, many value-added products such as starch, cassava flour, cassava chips, livestock feeds and ethanol are not adequately given attention and these products are mostly lost due to rudimentary methods of processing. The traditional techniques are time consuming with low production capacity. It is the opinion of this study that combined policies to address both cassava supply and processing constraints should be pursued to gain fully from the

potentials in cassava. This study finds justification on grounds that Nigeria is a key player in cassava production and for the country to maximize its capacity in cassava production, there is need to identify the technology in use in processing cassava and also the factors that inhibit the processing of the various cassava by-products in the states that have comparative advantage in cassava production. Such knowledge will enable the implementation of policies that encourage cassava value-addition.

On grounds of the aforesaid, the focus of this paper is to examine the nature of cassava processing techniques adopted by cassava processors in Imo state and also to investigate the factors which militate against the diversification of cassava processing into various cassava by-products in the state.

Empirical Review

The relevance of cassava to an economy has led to some studies carried out to investigate the factors that affect the utilization of its full capacity. In a study in Imo state, Osuji, Anyanwu, Ohajianya, and Oguoma (2015) carried out an evaluation study of cassava processing enterprise. The study adopted a multi-stage random sampling technique in which 106 respondents were selected.

Findings revealed that amongst the processed forms of cassava, *garri* accounted for 79.2 percent, *fufu* accounted for 71.7 percent and starch accounted for 26.4 percent. With respect to the processing techniques; harvesting, peeling, dewatering and sieving accounted for 100 percent. Another study in Imo state by Osuji, Anyanwu, Ehirim, Eze and Tim-Ashama (2017) investigated the economics of processed cassava products. The study used a multi-stage random sampling technique to select 106 cassava processors in the study area. Findings indicated that Okigwe and Owerri zones recorded the highest net returns in *garri* and *fufu* processing respectively.

Obayelu, Olaleke, Oke and Oladeji (2018) examined the factors that determine cassava processing and the economic benefits of cassava processing to processors in Yewa South Local Government Area of Ogun State. The study examined 80 cassava processors using multi-stage sampling procedure. The study found that majority of the processors adopted the traditional processing techniques, while *garri*, *lafun* and *fufu* were the main products from cassava processing. Factors such as funding, lack of electricity, good road network, labour cost and poor storage facilities were

found to constrain cassava processing in the area. In a related study, the factors that affect the indigenous processing of cassava into flour (*Alibo*) among rural women in Shendam local government area of Plateau State was investigated by Abdullahi and Danwanka (2018). The study randomly selected 120 respondents using structured questionnaire. Findings showed that the major obstacle to traditional cassava processing in the study area include, labour and processing implements, high costs of transport, very small quantities of cassava used per processing and poor pricing of products.

Agbaeze, Ohunye, Obamen and Ibe (2020) examined the problems and challenges that face the management of cassava processing in Nigeria. The study found that the level of mechanization, agricultural policy frameworks, poor infrastructure, access to capital and inadequate agricultural technical experts affect cassava processing in Nigeria. In a study in Oyo state, Adesope, Olumide-ojo, Oyewo, Ugege and Oyelade (2020) evaluated the costs and returns in cassava flour and *garri* production in addition to examining the factors that influence their production. The study adopted a two-stage sampling technique and findings indicate that transportation cost, peeling cost, grating

cost and the quantity of *garri* sold had significant impact on the total revenue of cassava flour sold. Also, inadequate capital, price, transportation among others were the factors that influenced *garri* and cassava production. In another study carried out in Imo state, Egwuonwu (2022) used structured questionnaire from 120 cassava processors selected through multi sampling technique to investigate the cassava processors' utilization of hygienic practices. The result revealed that majority of the respondents had a high knowledge of cassava processing hygienic practices which was utilized during processing. Factors such as lack of finance, lack of disposal facility and inadequate access to clean water were found to constrain processing hygienic practices in processing. In yet another study in Imo State, Esiobu, Osuji, Akande, Udunwa and Emeruwa (2023) investigated if farmers derive returns from cassava production. Finding reveals evidence of positive revenue from cassava production and that cassava production has been a veritable source of livelihood for farmers in the area. Factors such as inadequate capital and limited availability of farmland were observed to be the constraints that adversely affect farmers' production capacity.

Methodology

Research Design

In this paper, the survey method was adopted. This method was chosen because it is appropriate if current opinion of respondents concerning any phenomenon of interest is sought.

Study Area

This study was carried out in Imo State, Nigeria from February 2025 through June 2025. Imo state is located in the South-Eastern rainforest belt of Nigeria with a total of 27 Local Government Areas. The state has three Agricultural Zones namely; Owerri, Orlu and Okigwe. Agriculture is the main economic activity predominant amongst the people of these zones. The Local Government Areas considered in the study are Ngor Okpala and Aboh Mbaise for Owerri Zone, Ohaji-Egbema and Nwangele for Orlu Zone while Obowo and Isiala Mbano were selected from Okigwe Zone, thereby giving a total of six Local Government Areas. The areas selected are noted for their predominant agricultural activities mainly with regard to cassava production.

Sample Unit

The respondents for data collection in the study are cassava processors in each of the selected Local Government Areas.

Sampling Procedure

The study adopted a multi-stage sampling technique to select the respondents. This method is to ensure that the survey covers the entire State. In the first stage, two local government areas were purposively selected from each of the three Agricultural Zones. In the second stage, three Autonomous Communities were selected from each of the Local Government Areas, making a total of 18 communities. Finally, twelve cassava processors were randomly selected from each community, giving a total of 216 processors which formed the sample size.

Questionnaire Design

The instruments for data collection used are structured questionnaires which were streamlined and structured in a way to reflect the objectives of the study. The study used twelve (12) research assistants for data collection who focused in each community in order to ensure accuracy and efficiency.

Data Analysis

The study used non parametric statistical tools such as percentages, frequency distribution and means to analyze the data.

Results and Discussion

The results of the field survey are placed in the Tables below. Finding in Tables 1a and 1b concerning the socio-economic characteristics of cassava processors in the area indicated that first in Table 1a, of the individuals interviewed 29.3% are male while 70.7% are female. It is equally found that a preponderance of those interviewed who are into cassava processing fall in the age bracket of 41-50 and 51-60. In particular, while 43.5% fall within 41-50, 37.0% fall within 51-60. A handful of 7% fall below 30 years while also only 8.2% fall between 61 years and above. In the same vein, while 74.5% of the respondents are married, 25.5% are unmarried. Majority of the respondents (97%) has secondary school education while 27% has tertiary educational background. In terms of household size, while 42.9% has a household size of 4-6, 33.7% has household size of 1-3.

With respect to processing experience, finding in Table 1b indicates that 36.4% of

the respondents has less than 4 years of processing experience, 34.2% has experience that spanned between 5-10 years while a handful of 10.3% has experience that spanned from 21 years and above. The business size of 43.5% of the respondents fall within N90,100 and above while the business size of 4.3% of them fall below N30,000. A high percentage of the respondents (63.6%) use family labour in their business while 16.8% use hired labour. Majority of the respondents said that they sourced their capital from friends and relatives (34.8%) as well as from personal savings (26.1%), while few sourced theirs from commercial banks (2.2%). While 41.8% obtained their cassava tubers from personal cultivation, 24.5% said they bought theirs and 33.7% obtained their cassava tubers from both sources.

These socio-economic statistics of the cassava processors have some implications for cassava processing in Imo state. First, looking at the sex of those who are into the business, it is found that it is dominated by the female gender, implying that the men do not find it interesting. Equally, evidence

shows that young people are not too many into the business as it is dominated by those in the middle and old ages. Of importance in the finding is that a preponderance of the respondents has secondary school background while a few has tertiary educational background. These statistics present an ugly picture in cassava processing in the state since low productivity alongside crude method of processing is bound to exist. Young people as well as educated people are often dynamic and innovative and their active involvement in cassava processing will no doubt lead to an improvement in both technique and diversification into various cassava by-products. To make matters worse, the few years of processing experience possessed by many of the respondents is a testament that there is no sustainability in the business. Another major concern revealed in the finding is that majority of the processors still rely on their savings and assistance from family members to raise fund for the business. Only a tiny few patronize the conventional banks and raising funds through the cooperative is still alien to them.

Table 1 Socio-economic Characteristics of Cassava Processors in the Study Area

Socio-economic Characteristics	F (n = 184)	Percentage (%)	Mean (\bar{x})
Sex			
Male	54	29.3	0.7065
Female	130	70.7	
Age (Years)			
Less than 30	7	3.8	3.3804
31-40	14	7.6	
41-50	80	43.5	
51-60	68	37.0	
61 and above	15	8.2	
Marital Status			
Married	137	74.5	0.2554
Single	47	25.5	
Level of Education Years)			
Non Formal Education	18	9.8	2.7228
Primary	42	22.8	
Secondary	97	52.7	
Tertiary	27	14.7	
Household Size (No.)			
1-3	62	33.7	1.8967
4-6	79	42.9	
7 and above	43	23.4	

Source: Field Survey Data, 2025

Table 1b Other Socio-economic Characteristics of Cassava Processors in the Study Area

Socio-economic Characteristics	F (n = 184)	Percentage (%)	Mean (\bar{x})
Processing Experience			
Less than 4yrs	67	36.4	2.0326
5-10Yrs	63	34.2	
11-20Yrs	35	19.0	
21 Yrs and above	19	10.3	
Business Size			
Less than N30,000	8	4.3	2.5543
N30,100- N60,000	81	44.0	
N60,100- N90,000	15	8.2	
N90,100 and above	80	43.5	
Labour Source			
Family	117	63.6	1.5598
Hired	31	16.8	
Both	36	19.6	
Capital Source			
Micro-finance banks	23	12.5	3.1250
Thrift /Esusu	27	14.7	
Friend/Relatives	64	34.8	
Personal savings	48	26.1	
Co-operatives	18	9.8	
Commercial Banks	4	2.2	
Other Businesses Except Cassava Processing			
Yes	61	33.2	.6685
No	123	66.8	
Source of Cassava Tuber			
Cultivation	77	41.8	1.9185
Purchasing	45	24.5	
Both	62	33.7	

Source: Field Survey Data, 2025

With respect to the cassava by-products processed, it is found in Table 2 that three by-products namely: garri (83.2 percent), fufu (94.6 percent) and tapioca (77.21 percent) were largely processed. The dominance of both garri and fufu revealed in this present study is in line with the findings of past studies such as Osuji *et al.* (2015) and Obayelu, *et al.* (2018). It is not surprising these by-products are patronized highly given that those engaged in this business are mostly peasant farmers with low capital and mainly not too educated. In all the major markets and streets in Imo state,

one will find these by-products in their large supply; justifying that most people are into the business of processing them. The processing of animal feed, flour and starch is not given due attention as indicated in the finding. Yet, these by-products have enough value-addition (since they are used in the production of other products) and they have the potential to yield more profit than the traditional garri, fufu and tapioca since they have existing export market if processed well.

Table 2 Cassava By-products Processed

By-products	F (n = 184)	Percentage (%)
Garri	153	83.2
Fufu	174	94.6
Tapioca	142	77.21
Akara-akpu	31	6.8
Animal feed	29	15.8
Starch	65	35.3
Flour	33	17.9
Others	None	None

Source: Field Survey Data, 2025

To buttress further the reasons why cassava processing in the state is still at its rudimentary stage, the study examined the techniques employed by the processors. The results shown in Table 3 is evident that in all the techniques identified, majority of the

processors still use the manual or crude method of processing. Except for grating where majority of them use machine, the rest of other processing technique is manual. Worthy of note is that the use of machine for grating is typical of those who process garri

because of the existence of locally fabricated garri grinding machines. Even the tiny percentage that adopt modern technique in other forms of processing often use small home-made machines that cannot be used for large-scale processing. The high percentage use of manual method in the processing of cassava is an indication that modernizing cassava processing in the state

still requires serious official interventions. One major issue of concern is that unlike palm oil processing which has improved as a result of local fabrication of the processing machines, cassava processing mainly in the state has not enjoyed such opportunity. Though efforts have been made to provide some of these machines, yet their affordability and adoption remain a problem.

Table 3 Technique in Cassava Processing

Processing Technique	F (n = 184)	Percentage (%)	Mean (\bar{x})
Peeling			
Manual	164	89.1	0.1087
Machine	20	10.9	
Grating			
Manual	28	15.2	0.1522
Machine	158	84.8	
Dewatering			
Manual	163	88.6	0.1141
Machine	21	11.4	
Sieving			
Manual	164	89.1	0.1087
Machine	20	10.9	
Frying			
Manual	167	90.8	0.0924
Machine	17	9.2	
Parboiling			
Manual	168	91.3	0.0870
Machine	16	8.7	
Slicing			
Manual	170	92.4	0.0761
Machine	14	7.6	
Steaming			
Manual	171	92.9	.00707
Machine	13	7.1	
Fermentation			
Manual	171	92.9	0.0707
Machine	13	7.1	
Pounding			
Manual	166	90.2	.0978
Machine	18	9.8	

Source: Field Survey Data, 2025

Information in Table 4 reveals that a host of factors have been identified to militate against the diversification of cassava processing into different by-products. Chief among these factors as indicated by the respondents are being unaware of the opportunities that exist in these by-products, low finance, high cost of labour and low supply of cassava tubers. These factors are not peculiar to processors in Imo state as some studies in other parts of Nigeria have equally identified them such as the study conducted in Plateau State by Abdullahi and Danwanka (2018).

Since majority of the processors are not well educated, it is not surprising that they may not be aware that cassava can be processed into other forms other than the traditional fufu, garri and tapioca. Even if some of them are aware, the fact that they do not have the requisite finance and technological know-how will continue to pose an obstacle. The respondents complained of high cost of labour and low supply of cassava tubers. The source of labour used in the processing business as identified in the study is mainly family members. Only few use the services

of hired labourers yet the technique is manual which should have required many hands to enhance increased productivity. Considering their low capital and limited scale of production, it will be too expensive to hire labour. Also, cassava tuber sourcing poses a big challenge to the processors probably because the demand for cassava tubers is usually very high. Majority of the respondents indicated that they cultivate their own tubers and only few said they buy theirs. Considering the low scale of farming by these processors as they mostly farm for self-subsistence, one wonders how they are going produce enough that will be processed into large quantity of the traditional by-products not to talk of diversifying into other by-products.

The respondents were asked if they would like to be supported in cassava processing and majority of them answered in the affirmative as shown in appendix i. However, a few were indifferent which raised serious concern regarding the lackluster attitude of some farmers in the state who see any aspect of farming as part-time occupation.

Table 4 Factors Militating Against Diversification of Cassava Processing

Militating Factors	F (n = 184)	Percentage (%)
High cost of labour	147	79.9
Lack of access to processing equipment	66	35.9
Low supply of cassava tubers	144	78.3
Low market demand for the processed products	24	13.0
Unaware of the opportunities in these by-products	161	87.5
Lack of technological knowhow	94	51.1
Low finance	141	76.6
Constraints in marketing processed products	36	19.6

Source: Field Survey Data, 2025

Conclusion/Recommendation

The study finds that cassava processing business in the state is dominated by the female sex (70.7%). Also, while secondary school leavers (52.7%) pre-dominate in the processing, majority of them (36.4%) has less than four years of processing experience. Findings also reveal that the processors in the state still process more of the traditional cassava by-products such as fufu (83.2%), garri (94.6%) and tapioca (77.21%). Equally revealed in the study is that manual processing method still predominates in all the processing stages identified. These findings have some implications for improved cassava processing in Imo state. Rigid reliance on the processing of traditional by-products will definitely erode the gains inherent in the processing of other

by-products such as flour, starch and animal feed. These by-products have enough value-addition and if produced in large quantity and good quality, could have an export market. The danger of focusing on these traditional by-products is that even if some processors want to embrace the processing of flour or starch, they will surely face constraints in the supply of cassava tubers since the demand for the tubers in the processing of the traditional by-products is usually very high. Apart from this, the socio-economic characteristics of the identified cassava processors in the state are such that do not permit modernizing cassava processing by using advanced techniques. Majority of the processors are not educated just as they lack the requisite finance to purchase the modern tools even if the tools are available. With majorly less than four

years of processing experience, it implies that cassava processing business in the state is not carried out on a sustained basis. This scenario could adversely affect long-term planning to improve the business as well as affecting long-term loan acquisition by the processors.

This study is limited by its inability to cover the entire state since a few areas were studied. The peculiarities in the areas not studied could be concealed when generalization is made from the results of the sample. The authors are of the view that for cassava processing in the state to get to an advance stage where it will be beneficial to the individual processors and the state, first there is need to create awareness on the immense opportunities that exist in processing of cassava into flour, starch, animal feed, cassava chips and other by-products that have value-addition. With the awareness coupled with other incentives, young and educated people who are innovative will be attracted to the business. It is also recommended that a special funding scheme should be floated through which cassava processors will be assisted financially with low interest rate. To help boost their capital and also provide an avenue for collective initiatives, the study recommends that there is need to encourage the formation of sound cassava processors cooperatives in the state,

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